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Political Fanaticism through the Lens of the Local Community: A Case in Tagbilaran City, Bohol

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Abstract

An albatross that keeps weighing down Philippine politics is the overabundance of fanaticism and idolatry among Filipino citizens. As during every election, it has been part of the tradition to support and rally one's chosen candidate. This qualitative study seeks to investigate political fanaticism among voters in the local community of Tagbilaran City, Bohol using phenomenological design. The data were gathered in the three barangays in Tagbilaran City using a self-made interview guide to the thirty informants composed of fifteen males and fifteen females with age range based on Erik Erikson's Psychosocial stage of development. The data were analyzed and interpreted using the Six-Phase Approach to the Thematic Analysis of Braun & Clarke (2006). The results reveal that political fanaticism exists among voters because most of them relate their experiences with their involvement in campaign rallies and express their support through social media. It was also observed that the number of supporters, social media popularity, and good performance of the politicians are the basis of popularity among voters which affect their vote choice. Polls or surveys make voters aware of the rating of their supported candidate, whether he/she is leading the race or not, affecting the voters emotionally. Furthermore, most of the respondents agreed that polls or surveys helped them in their decision-making process on whom to vote for. Lastly, voters' knowledge of a candidate's character and work performance leads to political fanaticism creating loyalty among voters. With this political knowledge, voters can choose competent leaders to benefit the community.

Keywords: *political fanaticism, local community, political knowledge, psychosocial stage of development, phenomenological*

Introduction

Political fanaticism is one thing Filipinos are known for when it comes to politics. The popularity of the terms "diehard" in "diehard Duterte supporters" or DDS and "loyalist" in "Marcos loyalists" serves as evidence of this fanatic attitude. Consequently, political fanaticism can either make or break relationships. It results in the creation of boundaries from the local political unit to the national level. According to Contreras (2022), the albatross that keeps weighing down Philippine politics is the overabundance of fanaticism and idolatry among Filipino citizens. During every election, it has been part of the tradition to support and rally one's chosen candidate. Barbu (2021) used "fanatic" to describe individual and collective behavior. It denotes a particular political activity and a group (a party, a movement, or a goal-oriented organization) based on or driven by strong emotions and unwavering convictions. These three characteristics may be present in this group in one or more instances. Meanwhile, according to Calhoun (2004), "fanaticism is not merely a strong commitment to a worldview, ideology or belief system." Many people are devoted to a specific religion, ideology, or political system without being fanatics. A fanatic is deemed a right, as one's beliefs characterize fanaticism. It is regarded as connected to rationalism (Choraqui, 2019). Lorente (1995) cites that the cognitive substrate of fanaticism is rational cognition or consciousness. It attempts to establish the objectivity of a theory that stays in the form of representational cognition and manifests in the external world. According to Downs (1957), the diverseness of societies and social conflicts introduce uncertainty that leads to ideologies and ambiguity concerning social groups that may be more useful for electoral victory and, as a result, the differentiation of political party proposals. According to his rational choice theory, political parties seek to win elections not for any altruistic reason related to implementing a political program but for the prestige and benefits that come with being in power. The main objective of political parties is to win elections because electoral victories concretize the prestige and profits they seek. Polls play a significant role in knowing the public's choice of candidate for an upcoming election.

Research Questions

Accordingly, an albatross that keeps weighing down Philippine politics is the overabundance of fanaticism and idolatry among Filipino citizens. As during every election, it has been part of the tradition to support and rally one's chosen candidate. This study seeks to investigate political fanaticism among voters in the local community of Tagbilaran City, Bohol. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the voters in relation to political fanaticism?
2. Why popularity affects vote choice?
3. How do polls or surveys affect political fanaticism?
4. How come political knowledge leads to political fanaticism?
5. What are the significant themes that can be drawn out from their experience?

Literature Review

According to Rothschild and Malhotra (2019), the data gathered from polls influence the behavior of voters as it is a way to acquire information needed to make up their minds and decide whom to vote for. According to the Pulse Asia Survey and OCTA Research polls for the presidential and vice-presidential race and as reported by several media outlets, specific names lead the polls. Rappler regularly presented data from these polls chronologically, showing the movement of the public's sentiments at various times. As mentioned by Blais, Gidengi, and Nevitte (2002), pre-election polls influence voter choices. Additionally, the results demonstrate that voters favor candidates who score well in pre-election polls over those who do not. This supports the claims made by other academics on the bandwagon or contagion impact of pre-election polls. Also, in influencing vote choice, leader effects can be utilized in two possible ways: 1) capturing votes that belong to his/her party's competitors or 2) motivating people who otherwise would not vote at all to vote for his/her party (da Silva, 2018). Family can also affect a voter's choice of vote. Turan and Tıraş (2017), in the grafting of the political identity of the children, family is a significant factor. According to Argyle (2020), families are typically the 'starting point' for someone's political views. She added that these political perspectives are most similar to staying close to their parents' perspective if their parents talked about politics in their home growing hope. Attitudinal analysis of voting by Fishbein and Coombs (1974) examines the significant factors relevant to an individual's decision to vote and his choice of candidate. It makes the case that social factors are insufficient to predict political choices, particularly voting. Other important motivations, in addition to the civic duty to vote, are party identification, concern with problems, personal connection to candidates, opinions about the candidates' personalities, compliance with group standards, and the sensation of efficacy. Canare, Mendoza, and Lopez (2018) mentioned that people experiencing poverty are more likely to be the target of vote buying and vote selling. Data analysis of their study demonstrated that vote buying among people with low incomes is, in fact, widespread, but that incidence varies according to the type of vote buying. According to Cruz, Keefer, and Labonne (2015), vote buying effectively translates votes to the candidate.

According to the study of Pablo, Oco, Roldan, Cheng, and Roxas (2014), the three elements that determine the usage of social networking sites positively affect voters' political engagement, influencing voters' views toward voting and their trust in their judgment. Users' "want to join" and "perceived ease of use" of social networking sites, in particular, significantly increase their political engagement, as well as their attitude toward voting and confidence in their voting choices. Job insecurity affects people's political attitudes. According to Wiertz and Rodon (2021), voting is ultimately and partially ideology-driven and possibly strongly influenced by who is currently in power. Maboloc (2019) stated that political overlords control the lives of people. Job insecurity stems from the citizens having no decent means of living, which results in dependency. The fear of being unemployed has a shift in political preference (Selenko & De Witte, 2020). Social media sites like Twitter and Facebook allow users to interact where they express their thoughts freely and share information with other users. Arugay (2022) said that social media and electoral campaigns seem to make a perfect match. Furthermore, popularity on social media has become a significant element in determining how people vote. This phenomenon of popularity and its effects on the number of voters and social media is reflected in Dewi and Aminulloh's study (2016). Social media has developed into crucial instruments for spreading information and running campaigns. In a study, Lee, Yen, Chen, and Lin (2016) believed that examining human rationality in a political election is essential because a well-functioning democracy rests mainly upon the rational choices of individual voters. Additionally, Voters' trust, acceptance of policy suggestions, and overall support for a politician are all influenced by a candidate's popularity (Stier et al., 2018). According to Salisbury (1975), political participation is necessary for human life. Its level reflects the degree of democracy, which can be considered a right and obligation. Political participation has been defined as behavior that seeks to influence the policies, decisions, and actions of government, including its allocation of resources (Barner-Barry & Rosenwein, 1985; Milbrath, 1965; Verba et al., 1980; Washburn, 1982). Sugang (2006) added that there are forms of political participation, including voting, convincing others to vote for a particular candidate, joining a political party, donating money for a campaign, and contacting government officials. According to Kim (2022), upon knowing the survey results, voters may feel anxious or have a sense of pride, reinforcing confidence in their choice of candidate. According to Marcus (2000), emotions are a valuable and essential tool for decision-making. The study of Walgrave, Lefevere, and Tresch (2017) explains how voters' issue orientations might influence their voting decisions in three different ways. The impression of the parties' or candidates' views on many issues comes first. Voters are concerned about how closely candidates' or parties' positions align with their own and whether politicians and parties continue to support the same position. Perceived leadership qualities also play a crucial role in voters' decision-making. Candidates who exhibit strong leadership traits such as confidence, charisma, communication skills, and the ability to inspire and mobilize others may be viewed favorably by voters. Leadership qualities are often associated with the candidate's ability to address challenges, make sound decisions, and provide effective representation (Bass, 1990).

Methodology

This study utilized the qualitative approach in research using the phenomenological design. This study was conducted through face-to-face interviews and focus group discussions in the three barangays in Tagbilaran City: Tiptip, Cogon, and Booy. The researchers conducted an in-depth interview with thirty informants composed of fifteen males and fifteen females with ages ranging from 21 years old to 39 years old (young voters), 40 years old to 59 years old (middle-aged voters), and 60 years old and above (old age voters). The age categorization was based on Erik Erikson's Psychosocial stage of development. Such age selection is best suited for comparability on their views regarding their experiences of political fanaticism. The informants were chosen through the purposive sampling technique, where they were chosen purposely as their experiences were aligned with and corresponded to the study's objectives.

The researchers used a self-made interview guide that answered the questions about the voters' experiences in relation to political fanaticism, why popularity affects vote choice, and how polls or surveys affect political fanaticism. How does political knowledge lead to political fanaticism, and what are the significant themes that can be drawn out from their experience?

Before the conduct of the research, the research team secured approval from the academic authorities in the institutions. After the concerned university and barangay officials approved, the study underwent an ethics review by the University of Bohol Ethics Review Board. It ensured the principles of good research practice and enlightened about the research study's consequences and the informants' interests. The researchers ensured that the "Do-no-harm" was upheld throughout the research. The researchers obtained permission from the Office of the President, Vice President of Academic Affairs, Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences, and Student Affairs Office to conduct the study outside the campus. After their approval was acquired, the researchers wrote a letter of permission to the respective barangay captains for the study to be conducted. A consent letter was also included, stating that informants have anonymity during the process. Furthermore, they were informed of their right to voluntarily accept or reject their participation in the study and that they could stop answering the tool if they felt their rights were being violated. The contact numbers of the researchers were added to the letter of consent for them to reach out if they had issues during and after the data gathering. The utterances gathered were analyzed using thematic analysis, a qualitative data analysis technique that involves examining a data set for recurring patterns and then interpreting and reporting on them.

Results and Discussion

This study revealed that their experiences concerning political fanaticism are being involved in campaign rallies and considered competent public service among politicians. They shared that they became political fanatics by being influenced by competent public service and expressing support through campaigns, including social media. It implies that political participation is crucial in democratic countries because it allows people to keep their elected representatives accountable and have the role on how their country is governed. Traditionally, political participation has taken the form of voting, joining political parties, attending political rallies, and contacting elected officials (Ahmad & Said, 2019). Generally, popularity is based on the number of supporters, their presence on social media, and the excellent performance of the politicians, which affect their vote choice. According to Stier et al., (2018), voter's trust, acceptance of policy suggestions and overall support for a politician are all influenced by a candidate's popularity. Moreover, voters are influenced by a candidate's competence which involves their knowledge. It signifies that people likely do not vote for someone perceived as lacking experience and ability to handle a government official's job. Candidates perceived as strong and inspiring leaders are much more likely to be preferred by the voters. Lee et al. (2016) affirms that examining human rationality in a political election is essential because a well-functioning democracy rests mainly upon the rational choices of individual voters.

Polls or surveys affect political fanaticism because they believe that their awareness of rating emotionally affects them. The majority also agrees that polls or surveys are helpful in voting choice because they indicate competence and provide them with insights. It gives to what Rothschild & Malhotra (2019) mentioned that the data gathered from polls influence the behavior of voters as it is a way to acquire information needed to make up their minds and decide whom to vote for. Upon knowing the survey results, voters may feel anxious or have a sense of pride, reinforcing confidence in their choice of candidate (Kim, 2022). Knowledge of a candidate's character and work performance leads to political fanaticism. Moreover, political knowledge enables them to choose a capable and qualified leader. According to Nai & Maier (2016), candidates with a track record of relevant achievements or expertise in areas of importance to voters may be perceived as more competent and capable of effectively fulfilling the responsibilities of the position they seek.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, it can be concluded that political fanaticism exists among voters in Tagbilaran City, Bohol because most of them relate their experiences with their involvement in campaign rallies and express their support through social media. It was also observed that the number of supporters, social media popularity, and good performance of the politicians are the basis of popularity among voters, affecting their vote choice. Polls or surveys make voters aware of the rating of their supported candidate, whether he/she is leading the race or not, which affects the voters emotionally. Furthermore, the majority of the respondents agreed that polls or surveys helped them in their decision-making process on whom to vote for. Lastly, voters' knowledge of a candidate's character and work performance leads to political fanaticism. It creates loyalty among voters. With this political knowledge, voters can choose competent leaders to benefit the community.

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